

Sustainable Digitalisation: Shaping the Future of Agriculture

HIGHLIGHTS REPORT

25 JANUARY 2024

How can digitalisation reshape the agricultural landscape, and contribute to a sustainable future for farming?

On 25 January 2024, the [European Association for Innovation in Local Development \(AEIDL\)](#) hosted the inaugural [CODECS Knowledge Transfer Accelerator](#) webinar on “[Sustainable Digitalisation: Shaping the Future of Agriculture](#)”. With 90 participants from over 30 EU and international countries, the event considered the present state of play on the relationship between European agriculture and rural digitalisation and its impact on sustainability goals.

[Serafin Pazos-Vidal](#), Senior Expert in Rural and Territorial Development at AEIDL opened the session by emphasising CODECS’ mission to contribute to sustainable digitalisation, highlighting the importance of evidence-based insights from Horizon Europe projects amidst current policy contexts post-2027, including discussions on the future of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and upcoming CAP and Cohesion proposals in May 2025.

The webinar unveiled the [CODECS Digital Platform](#), a dynamic hub dedicated to showcasing cutting-edge digital tools and research outputs aimed at promoting technology adoption aligned with sustainable digital visions.

Insights from ongoing and past Horizon Europe projects, namely [BEATLES](#) and [UNISECO](#), were presented, offering a comprehensive perspective on digitalisation in agriculture.

The webinar was organised within the framework of the new [CODECS Knowledge Accelerator](#), which is CODECS activities aimed to transfer the key outputs of the project and engage with key external stakeholders. [Merveille Ntabuhashe](#) of AEIDL concluded the session by inviting participants to join the Knowledge Accelerator (KA) Community and partake in future network activities.

ORGANISER:

 25 JANUARY 2024

 ONLINE

 91 PARTICIPANTS
(research, public authorities, advisors, business, producers, other EU-funded projects, etc.)

 33 COUNTRIES

 PRESENTATIONS AND RECORDINGS [HERE](#)

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Understanding CODECS and the idea of sustainable digitalisation

Gianluca Brunori

Full Professor, University of Pisa & CODECS Coordinator

Gianluca Brunori, from the [University of Pisa](#) & CODECS Coordinator, presented the [CODECS](#) project and its vision on sustainable digitalisation.

Digitalisation is a socio-technical transformation that must be analysed with a systemic view. The overarching goal of CODECS is “to improve the collective capacity to understand, assess, and foresee the full range of benefits and costs of farm digitalisation, and to build digital ecosystems that maximise the net benefits of digitalisation.”

The [CODECS](#) (maximising the CO-benefits of agricultural Digitalisation through conducive digital ECoSystems) Project is structured around 20 Living Labs to introduce digital technologies and assess their impacts. He emphasised the contextual nature of digitalisation, by underlining the importance of considering its impact on aspects beyond the technical

sphere, such as its effects on social and environmental factors. The project was structured around **four key components** aimed at enhancing understanding of policy needs in the digitalisation of agriculture:

- **Co-benefits:** comprehensive understanding of how costs and benefits are distributed among different social groups.
- **(Digital) resources** necessary to ensure sustainable digitalisation practices.
- **Capabilities** needed to generate positive outcomes for multiple stakeholders.
- **Digital Ecosystems:** delving into how digital ecosystems generate resources and capabilities while influencing the distribution of costs and benefits. Emphasising the operational context at the farm level, this analysis provides insights into various factors influencing the process of digitalisation.”

CODECS Digital Platform

Anna Selini Petropoulou

Research Associate, Agricultural University of Athens

Anna Petropoulou, from the [Agricultural University of Athens](#), introduced the [CODECS Digital Platform](#) during the event. The platform serves as a new **dynamic hub for showcasing state-of-the-art digital tools and research**, promoting technology adoption in line with sustainable digital practices. Its integrated infrastructure offers a centralised control panel, empowering users to conveniently access and oversee available resources through a unified interface.

The platform serves as an **inventory of datasets** stored by CODECS partners and provides a meta-inventory of digital technologies. Users can access open datasets and explore available technical solutions tailored to their needs, drawing from past inventories of projects like [DESIRA](#) (Digitisation:

Economic and Social Impacts in Rural Areas). Following an adaptive process to accommodate evolving technologies and user needs, the platform seeks to ensure long-term usability of the data stored, beyond project completion.

In her presentation, Anna Petropoulou highlighted upcoming development of a multicriteria assessment tool, with ongoing input from Living Labs and demonstration sessions to collect data. The toolkit will be integrated into the CODECS platform for easy access. All results will be compiled into an interactive storybook format for easy use.

Everyone is welcome to [sign in on the platform](#), which will continue to evolve with additional features and information.

Figure 1. CODECS Digital Platform, Meta-inventory

Group discussion

The first half of the session concluded with a group discussion, during which participants were encouraged to ask questions to the speakers.

Christof Schroth from Fraunhofer and former DESIRA partner inquired about the **CODECS definition and understanding of “digital platform”**. Gianluca Brunori responded by emphasising the ongoing process of defining a platform within the context of CODECS. He highlighted the importance of facilitating interaction, resource sharing, and collaboration among actors, rather than merely serving as a repository for information. Prof. Brunori stressed the significance of considering the platform’s goals, concepts, actors, rules, and shared resources in its development to ensure alignment with the project’s objectives.

Clare Sullivan from the Agricultural University of Athens asked more details regarding the **collection of the databases of the Digital Platform**. Anna Petropoulou clarified that data is gathered from surveys conducted within Living Labs and through broader feedback mechanisms, including research outputs from CODECS such as Living Labs and workshops. She noted that the data is presently undergoing analysis and processing before its incorporation into the platform’s database.

Serafin Pazos Vidal inquired about **encountered issues with the set-up and user-friendliness of the platform and the way the Living Labs are interacting with them, and how they have done to overcome that**. In response, Anna Petropoulou elaborated on the approach taken, stating that

they conducted surveys and targeted questions to understand the preferred utilisation of the tools within Living Labs. Furthermore, they developed mockups of the interface, which were shared with partners and stakeholders. Additionally, they organised interactive workshops with Living Labs to solicit their perspectives and feedback, facilitating adjustments as necessary.

Finally, Gerald Schwarz from Thünen-Institute of Farm Economics asked about **the level at which CODECS expects the data tools to be utilised** – either within or across the Living Labs, or both. He also inquired whether the project is developing data tools for internal or for external use.

Gianluca Brunori shared that through demonstrations, CODECS’ goal is to disseminate the tools beyond the Living Labs. The project encompasses 20 Living Labs, with a wide range of technologies, varying from advanced to basic level of development. The overarching objective is to analyse all these technologies uniformly and develop tools that can ideally be shared across all Living Labs and beyond.

Focus on EU Horizon Projects: Collaborative Insights

In the second part of the event, we provided **insights from past and ongoing Horizon Europe projects**. This allowed for a deeper exploration of the subject and offered a comprehensive perspective on digitalisation in agriculture.

Marilena Gemtou

Senior Researcher, Agricultural University of Athens
& BEATLES Project Manager

Marilena Gemtou (AUA) presented **BEATLES** (Behavioural Change Towards Climate-Smart Agriculture) – a 4-year Horizon Europe project that commenced in July 2022, and involving 18 partners across 10 EU countries. The project's primary objective is to **promote long-term and large-scale transitions to sustainable and Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA)**. It addresses various barriers, including economic, social, environmental, and policy-related factors, aiming to develop business models and policy recommendations.

The project employs **five case studies** across five EU countries to test the project's validity and draw lessons that will shape its inputs. These case studies represent value chains amounting to 45% of the agrifood sector in Europe.

The BEATLES project engages multiple stakeholders, ranging from farmers and business advisors to representatives from the agrifood industry, policy advisors, researchers, consumers, and civil society. These stakeholders, representing diverse EU regions and agricultural systems, actively participate in various activities that serve as the foundation for the project's work and conclusions. Since the beginning of the project, a wide range of co-creation activities have been done with a wide range of stakeholders, namely five systematic reviews, one survey targeting 720 farmers and another targeting 1220 consumers, 78 interviews with industry stakeholders across the five use cases and five co-creation workshops. These activities have led to a variety of key findings.

Figure 2. BEATLES key findings

To wrap up, Marilena Gemtou discussed the **challenges encountered during the project**. These challenges encompassed difficulties in recruiting a sufficient number of participants, implementing research with farmers due to language barriers, stakeholders' struggle to perceive the benefits of participation, and the necessity for a more bottom-up approach in research design to grasp the specificities of each use case. She emphasised that this approach requires substantial effort to ensure comprehensive engagement throughout the entire process, understanding the behavioural change and the concept of fairness.

Gerald Schwarz

Researcher, Thünen-Institute of Farm Economics

Gerald Schwarz from the [Thünen-Institute of Farm Economics](#) presented [UNISECO](#) (Understanding and Improving the Sustainability of Agro-ecological Farming Systems in the EU), a Horizon 2020 research project that concluded in April 2021. The aim of the project was to develop innovative approaches to enhance understanding of socio-economic and policy drivers and barriers for the further **development and implementation of agro-ecological practices in EU farming systems**.

A key priority of the project was to assess the roles and interactions of various actors involved, considering **implications towards sustainability**. It examined systems at the local level, using living labs as the foundation, and subsequently, it explored policy design and recommendations through various scenarios.

The project established a series of EU and local Multi-Actor Platforms ([MAPs](#)), each comprising small groups of 10-15 stakeholders to facilitate active engagement. These MAPs were dedicated to addressing real problems and opportunities faced by land managers in the area. Hence, the project ensured the direct involvement of real farms in the process to enhance the practical value of the conclusions.

Gerald Schwarz presented two key best practices exemplifying the MAP approach:

- 1. Sustainability Assessment of farming systems:** Local stakeholders actively participated in designing and contributing to the datasets, despite the challenging and time-consuming nature of the process. Each case study was intentionally kept small to ensure ease of management in terms of training and capacity building.
- 2. Social Network Analysis:** Effective and robust data collection was essential, mirroring the methodology used in CODECS, where story maps were compiled and presented accordingly.

Lastly, he shared key lessons learned during the completion of this project. These included the significance of meticulously planning, defining, and budgeting for data strategy and collection; leveraging datasets beyond archiving to enhance user-friendliness; establishing robust protocols for data harmonisation; recognising data ownership; and improving the usability and accessibility of digital solutions for various actors in the value chain, bridging producers and consumers.

Group discussion

During the group discussion, Foto Pappa (PhD student at the Sant' Anna School of Advanced Studies) directed a question to Marinela Gemtou regarding **the business model utilised in the BEATLES project and the significance of fairness within it**.

Marilena outlined that the project's core objective revolves around understanding barriers and subsequently crafting business models based on these insights. The project seeks to discern the behavioural shifts farmers have made from traditional to smart farming practices and how fairness (such as fair prices) is perceived across the value chain. This exploration aims to gauge farmers' perspectives on fairness and inform the development of business models grounded in these principles and conclusions.

To continue the discussion, an EU representative in the audience asked about the **process of selecting case studies that could best represent the diverse agricultural landscape** of the EU during the BEATLES project. In his inquiry, he noted, for example, the significant differences between the pig sector in Denmark and in other countries of Europe.

In response, Marinela explained that the selection process occurred during the project's development stage, engaging partners and countries capable of executing use cases that were representative of their respective regions. The project selected a representative farming sector in key countries and established networks of stakeholders for the co-creation activities. Although the selection may not encompass the entirety of the EU, strategic choices were made to facilitate the research process effectively.

Next steps: CODECS Knowledge Accelerator

Merveille Ntabuhashe

Project Manager, European Association for Innovation in Local Development (AEIDL)

Merveille Ntabuhashe, Project Manager at AEIDL, concluded the webinar by introducing the [CODECS Knowledge Accelerator \(KA\)](#), a virtual space dedicated to supporting stakeholders in evaluating the impact of digital agriculture on sustainability goals through peer-to-peer learning.

The CODECS KA will execute eight acceleration actions, including thematic webinars, online summer courses, and science-policy interface meetings. These activities aim to disseminate results and progress from the CODECS project to a broader audience.

The upcoming KA science-policy interface meeting will centre on “**Sustainable Digitalisation in Agriculture and Rural Areas**”,

providing participants with a comprehensive understanding of the policy environments related to digitalisation in agriculture and rural areas. It will also reflect on the role of the Multi-Actor Approach (MAA) and research in promoting the sustainable adoption of digitalisation in agriculture and rural areas. The date for this event will be announced very soon.

In conclusion, a **Knowledge Accelerator Community** has been established on LinkedIn to connect and foster knowledge sharing among actors active in the digitalisation of agriculture, rural development, and policies. Interested actors can register to join the KA Community [here](#).

Figure 3. CODECS Knowledge Accelerator

